

Antibody Characterization Report for Slit-2 (Slit homolog 2 protein)

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Protein name used in this report: Slit-2

Recommended protein name: Slit homolog 2 protein

Gene name: *SLIT2*

Uniprot: O94813

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized ten Slit-2 commercial antibodies for western blot and immunoprecipitation, using a standardized experimental protocol [2] based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. We identified many well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. An HAP1 *SLIT2* KO line is available at Horizon discovery and was used in this study. Expression of Slit-2 protein in HAP1 is adequate as determined through DepMap [3, 4].

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC006315c012	CVCL_TP41	HAP1	SLIT2 KO

Table 2: Summary of the Slit-2 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab134166**	GR34446361	AB_2620141	recombinant-mono	EPR2771	rabbit	2.14	Wb
Abcam	ab246503**	GR33570655	AB_3094797	recombinant-mono	EPR23272-227	rabbit	0.46	Wb
abcam	ab281068**	1107104-9	AB_3720093	recombinant-mono	EPR23154-101	rabbit	0.99	ELISA
abcam	ab281218**	1113698-3	AB_3720094	recombinant-mono	EPR23154-109	rabbit	1.01	ELISA
Abcam	ab7665	GR30880954	AB_449621	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb,IF
Abclonal	A3467**	4000002010	AB_2863066	recombinant-mono	ARC2010	rabbit	3.00	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	47600**	1	AB_2799327	recombinant-mono	E8W7Y	rabbit	0.00	Wb
GeneTex	GTX118220	43208	AB_10618954	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.17	Wb,IP
Proteintech	20217-1-AP	00083366	AB_10805766	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.80	Wb,IF
Proteintech	28730-1-AP	00117338	AB_2935470	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.60	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-42813**	XH3670297	AB_2911954	recombinant-mono	1T5A3	rabbit	1.90	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-31133	XH3669464D	AB_2548607	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.17	Wb,IP

Wb=western blot, IF=immunofluorescence, IP= immunoprecipitation, **=recombinant antibody, *=monoclonal antibody

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All the Slit-2 antibodies tested are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamate (Wisent cat. number 609065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201). Cells were starved in DMEM high-glucose containing L-glutamate and penicillin/ streptomycin.

Antibody screening by western blot on culture medium

HAP1 WT and *SLIT2* KO (listed in Table 1) were washed 3x with PBS 1x and starved for ~18 hrs. Culture media were collected and centrifuged for 10 min at 500 x g to eliminate cells and larger contaminants, then for 10 min at 4500 x g to eliminate smaller contaminants. Culture media were concentrated by centrifuging at 4000 x g for 30min using Amicon Ultra-15 Centrifugal Filter Units with a membrane NMWL of 10kDa (MilliporeSigma cat. number UFC901024). Culture media were supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340).

Western blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [5]. Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer from bio-Rad (cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106)

or Clarity Western ECL Substrate from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture medium

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [6]. Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (rabbit antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

Starved HAP1 WT media were concentrated as described above and supplemented with protease inhibitor. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of protein were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels. Prot-A:HRP (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8651) was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 2 µg/ml.

Figure 1: Slit-2 antibody screening by western blot on culture medium

Figure 2: Slit-2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture medium

Figure 1: Slit-2 antibody screening by western blot on culture medium.

HAP1 WT and *SLIT2* KO were cultured in serum free media, and 40 µg of protein from concentrated culture media were processed for western blot with the indicated Slit-2 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: ab134166** at 1/1000, ab246503** at 1/1000, ab281068** at 1/200, ab281218** at 1/200, ab7665 at 1/200, A3467** at 1/1000, 47600** at 1/1000, GTX118220 at 1/1000, 20217-1-AP at 1/1000, 28730-1-AP at 1/1000, MA5-42813** at 1/1000, PA5-31133 at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 170 kDa. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 2: Slit-2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on culture medium.

Immunoprecipitation was performed on concentrate culture media from HAP1 WT, and using 2.0 µg of the indicated Slit-2 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the indicated Slit-2 antibody. For western blot, MA5-42813** was used at 1/1000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate; n/s=non-specific signal. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

References

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